

3D MODELING OF HAND PROSTHESIS

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Abstract - The paper will introduce an upper limb prosthetics development process, focused on design and manufacturing using 3D modeling and printing technologies. The prosthetics of the upper limb and, in particular, arm prostheses represent the enabling tool in the rehabilitation process for subjects who have lost motor or structural functions because of amputation or congenital malformations. 3D modeling allows for the creation of customized and functional prosthetics, which can serve purposes from basic aesthetic models to advanced myoelectric prostheses. Besides, 3D printing reduces production time and costs when compared to traditional methods; therefore, prosthetics will be more available and fitted for specific purposes. This work points out how to 3D model a prosthetic hand, beginning from anatomical considerations up to computational simulations of material strength. The study also deals with the selection of appropriate materials and modular design with which prosthetic devices are functionally user-friendly.

Keywords - 3D modeling, 3D printing, arm prosthesis, customization, material strength, myoelectric prosthetics..

I. INTRODUCTION

Prostheses, particularly for upper limbs, represent an extremely relevant tool in the rehabilitation process of individuals who have lost, through amputation or congenital malformation, partially or completely, the motor or structural function of their limbs. In addition to restoring functions, such prostheses also have a great impact on self-esteem and social reintegration [1]. From the first rudimentary models made of wood and metal, the evolution has kept prostheses in constant scientific and technological progress until their modern and technologically advanced versions [2]. In the current context, 3D modeling and printing are among the digital technologies that are bringing a new vision in the manufacture of prostheses, allowing the production of highly functional and personalized devices [3].

These prostheses can range from simple models that could offer only aesthetic function to sophisticated myoelectric prostheses, which respond to muscle impulses and allow a wide range of movements. The development of these techno-

logies is underway to produce devices that mimic the natural arm both in appearance and dexterity [4].

3D Modeling Technology 3D modeling is an important technology in the development of prosthetic arms due to the enormous possibility it opens for individualized devices that fit the anatomical structure of the patient. In situations related to arm amputation, the 3D scanning of the residual limb is of great importance in relation to the fit and functional aspects of a prosthesis. This precise fit is important not only for the mechanical support of the prosthesis but also to avoid any discomfort or sores due to an inadequate fit or spare parts and materials that can cause friction with the skin causing irritations [5].

A great advantage of using 3D modeling for the development of prostheses is the possibility of creating modular parts, which can be adjusted and customized according to each user, in addition to allowing the coupling of new mechanisms later. In the case of more sophisticated prostheses, such as myoelectric ones, it is also possible to incorporate sensors and actuators that will allow prosthetic movements through the capture of muscle signals from the residual limb [6]. This level of customization and modularity makes 3D modeling an indispensable technology in the field of arm prostheses.

Application 3D printing, also known as additive manufacturing, has restructured the way arm prostheses are created. The process allows complex parts to be made much faster, thus increasing accessibility to prostheses and reducing production costs. For patients who need arm prostheses, 3D printing offers the possibility of rapid manufacturing, so that devices can be installed and provided in days, not weeks or even months [3].

In addition, 3D printing allows the creation of functional prostheses that are lightweight; this is an important feature when it comes to arm prosthesis users, who need to balance between weight and functionality [7]. It allows the creation of prostheses whose joints will provide simulation for the natural movement of the arm, from simple tasks such as opening or closing the hand to complex tasks, such as wrist rotation.

The other great advantage of 3D printing is aesthetic customization. Realistic skin color and texture, or a more futuristic and stylized look, all these are options available for prosthesis users based on preference. This is very important in relation to arm prostheses because of the identification element that the

device would have directly on the user. [8]

Material Context The functionality and durability of prostheses depend greatly on the choice of material. The materials should not be heavy to avoid overburdening the users, but still strong enough to withstand repetitive movements along with the forces applied in daily activities. The application of polymers for hand or arm prostheses has become quite widespread due to their lightweight and strength. Materials such as polylactic acid (PLA) and acrylonitrile butadiene styrene (ABS) are commonly used in printing the external structure of the prosthesis due to their characteristic balance between rigidity and flexibility and, comparatively, low cost [9].

However, more complex arm prostheses, with mechanical joints or myoelectric control, require more advanced materials and techniques. Polyether ether ketone (PEEK) is widely used in high-performance prostheses, being lightweight, strong, and biocompatible. Thermoplastic polyurethane (TPU) is a flexible and wear-resistant polymer used in components that need flexibility — for example, finger joints or palm structures [10].

In addition to polymers, metals also play an important role in the manufacture of structural components of prostheses, especially for joints with higher loads, such as elbows and wrists. Among these, titanium is one of the most preferred materials due to its lightweight with high strength. Biocompatibility provides safety for longer use, while its reduced weight protects the user from feeling overburdened during wear [11].

Challenges and Future Despite the extraordinary development of upper limb prostheses with the help of 3D modeling and printing technologies, many challenges remain. Among these, improving the integration of users and prostheses is one of the most important, particularly in myoelectric prostheses that require fine control to be performed by the patient. As for other important limitations, arm and hand prostheses fall short in a very important feature: tactile feedback. Users cannot “feel” the objects they are holding when using a prosthesis, which can limit functionality.

With this, this article seeks to go through all the stages that consist of planning and 3D modeling of a prosthesis for 3D printing. Anatomical issues involved, degrees of freedom, the initial control system, as well as computational tests of material resistance will be addressed.

II. METHODOLOGY

The anatomy of the hand is complex, with differentiation in its various types of thumb movements and the rest of the fingers. While the thumb can perform flexion, extension, abduction, adduction, opposition, and reposition movements, the other fingers have flexion, extension, abduction (radial deviation), adduction (ulnar deviation) movements, in addition to the wrist rotation movement that completes all movements.

Thus, based on the anatomical understanding of the hand, a prosthesis model was developed, with the defined degrees of movement being finger flexion and extension and the possibility of later implementing wrist rotation.

In the development of the device, the fingers were made in two rigid structures, one being the proximal phalanx and

the other the medial and distal phalanx interconnected without movement between these last two. It is possible to observe in figure 1 the standard model developed for all fingers, with the only difference between one finger and another being their dimensions.

Figura 1: 3D image in Fusion 360 software of the finger modeling with its respective moving parts.

To enable finger movement, two rods were placed interconnecting the fixation point that will be on the back of the hand to the distal phalanx of the finger, as seen in figure 2. Additionally, the distal phalanx is connected to the proximal phalanx, and this entire system allows for finger flexion and extension movement.

Figura 2: 3D image in Fusion 360 software of the finger modeling, without the proximal phalanx visible, with the fixation rods evident.

Thus, the whole set and its functioning allow the fingers to have a maximum flexion of 79° between the distal and proximal phalanx. And flexion of 66° between the proximal phalanx and its fixation point on the back of the hand.

In the development of the back and palm of the hand, there are some challenges to be considered. The main one is related to the accommodation of the motors and the prosthesis control system, as the space limit is a limiting factor, making it necessary to look for small-sized mechanics that are capable of providing the necessary force to hold the most common objects, such as cups, bottles, and other everyday items.

To this end, a movement mechanism was developed using a trapezoidal screw, which will be coupled to the motor shaft, and its rotation will be able to move the finger. The exemplifi-

cation of its operation can be seen in figure 3 below.

Figura 3: Demonstrative image of the movement system with the motor shaft and the lead screw that, when connected to the finger, can perform the flexion and extension movements of the finger. Adapted from R. Mio 2017. [12]

For the development of the entire 3D model of the prosthesis, the Fusion 360 software from Autodesk was used, a software that allows advanced model constructions. Additionally, it is possible to perform simulations of the movements of the parts, allowing computational tests to be carried out to verify mechanical interactions, thus avoiding possible design errors. The software also allows for studies and applied forces to determine the points of greatest force and torque applied, enabling an understanding of how the system dynamics work, allowing the simulation of the use of different types of printing materials, thus being able to choose the material that meets the project requirements. In figure 4, there is an example of a simulation with ABS material.

Figura 4: Computational simulation with a force of 100N being applied to the fingertip in the direction of the flexion movement, showing the points of minimum force received along the device and the maximum point, being a critical point for possible material fracture for this applied force.

III. RESULTS

After advancing through all stages of prosthesis development, from its aesthetic planning following anatomy, its definition of degrees of freedom, its initial control system planning, we can arrive at the complete development of a hand prosthesis, where the combination of all individual elements forms the final device. In figure X below, we can see how the elements form the hand and the final device made for 3D printing using ABS (Acrylonitrile Butadiene Styrene) material, being

a lightweight material with good resistance, the prosthesis can be used for activities that require a low degree of mechanical force, that is, it can be used for everyday activities such as holding cups, pens, and simple items that have low weight.

Figura 5: Image of the final prototype of the developed prosthesis with positioned fingers and complete palm model.

IV. CONCLUSIONS

In the future, it is expected that prosthetic arms will be much more advanced with innovations in areas such as bio-engineering and the addition of tactile sensors, possibly replicating the experience of a naturally living arm for users. Research into new materials, such as conductive polymers and biological tissue printing, also offers interesting possibilities for the development of arm prostheses that are sensitive to touch, or even connecting directly to the user's nervous system.

This extreme customization with 3D modeling and manufacturing will further evolve to make arm prostheses more integrated into patients' lives, both functionally and aesthetically. Combining these innovations certainly ensures that each morning, the field of prosthetics will revolutionize arm prostheses to the point where they will not only be a medical solution but an extension of the human body.

We can conclude that the evolution of upper limb prostheses, driven by the use of new technologies such as 3D modeling and printing, has brought significant advances in the rehabilitation and restoration of aesthetic functions for individuals with amputations or congenital malformations. The innovations introduced not only restore motor functions but also play an important role in the self-esteem and social reintegration of their users. 3D modeling and printing allow the creation of personalized devices that mimic the appearance and dexterity of the natural hand, highlighting the ongoing importance of their technological development. Thus, the combination of all the elements of personalization, aesthetics, and functionality offered by current prostheses represents a milestone in improving the quality of life for patients.

IV. REFERENCES

- [1] N. Kerver, S. van Twillert, B. Maas, and C. K. van der Sluis, "User-relevant factors determining prosthesis choice in persons with major unilateral upper limb defects: A meta-synthesis of qualitative literature and focus group results," *PLoS One*, vol. 15, no. 6, p. e0234342, 2020.
- [2] P. Kyberd, *Making hands: a history of prosthetic arms*. Academic Press, 2021.
- [3] J. M. Zuniga, A. M. Carson, J. M. Peck, T. Kalina, R. M. Srivastava, and K. Peck, "The development of a low-cost three-dimensional printed shoulder, arm, and hand prostheses for children," *Prosthetics and orthotics international*, vol. 41, no. 2, pp. 205–209, 2017.
- [4] N. Sakib and M. K. Islam, "Design and implementation of an emg controlled 3d printed prosthetic arm," in *2019 IEEE International Conference on Biomedical Engineering, Computer and Information Technology for Health (BECITHCON)*, pp. 85–88, IEEE, 2019.
- [5] R. Salazar-Gamarra, R. Seelaus, J. V. L. da Silva, A. M. da Silva, and L. L. Dib, "Monoscopic photogrammetry to obtain 3d models by a mobile device: a method for making facial prostheses," *Journal of Otolaryngology-Head & Neck Surgery*, vol. 45, no. 1, p. 33, 2016.
- [6] M. Buzzi, G. Colombo, G. Facoetti, S. Gabbiadini, and C. Rizzi, "3d modelling and knowledge: tools to automate prosthesis development process," *International Journal on Interactive Design and Manufacturing (IJIDeM)*, vol. 6, pp. 41–53, 2012.
- [7] I. Vujaklija and D. Farina, "3d printed upper limb prosthetics," *Expert review of medical devices*, vol. 15, no. 7, pp. 505–512, 2018.
- [8] J. Ten Kate, G. Smit, and P. Breedveld, "3d-printed upper limb prostheses: a review," *Disability and Rehabilitation: Assistive Technology*, vol. 12, no. 3, pp. 300–314, 2017.
- [9] R. Alturkistani, S. Devasahayam, R. Thomas, E. L. Colombini, C. A. Cifuentes, S. Homer-Vanniasinkam, H. A. Wurdemann, and M. Moazen, "Affordable passive 3d-printed prosthesis for persons with partial hand amputation," *Prosthetics and orthotics international*, vol. 44, no. 2, pp. 92–98, 2020.
- [10] C. Valenti, M. I. Federici, F. Masciotti, L. Marinucci, I. Xhimitiku, S. Cianetti, and S. Pagano, "Mechanical properties of 3d printed prosthetic materials compared with milled and conventional processing: A systematic review and meta-analysis of in vitro studies," *The Journal of Prosthetic Dentistry*, vol. 132, no. 2, pp. 381–391, 2024.
- [11] R. Rodriguez Colon, V. V. Nayak, P. E. Parente, P. Leucht, N. Tovar, C. C. Lin, K. Rezzadeh, J. H. Hacquebord, P. G. Coelho, and L. Witek, "The presence of 3d printing in orthopedics: A clinical and material review," *Journal of Orthopaedic Research®*, vol. 41, no. 3, pp. 601–613, 2023.
- [12] R. Mio, B. Villegas, L. Ccorimanya, K. M. Flores, G. Salazar, and D. Elías, "Development and assessment of a powered 3d-printed prosthetic hand for transmetacarpal amputees," in *2017 3rd International Conference on Control, Automation and Robotics (ICCAR)*, pp. 85–90, 2017.